

DR. PREETI YADAV, Professor Amity University Rajasthan Jaipur-302018 (Rajasthan)

DR. JEET SINGH, Officiating Principal & Head, Department of Commerce, Mahamaya Government Degree College, Sherkot, Distt. Bijnor – 246747 (U.P.)

e-mail: py1717@rediffmail.com ; jsy2626@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

The outbreak of COVID-19 has impacted countries in a massive way, especially the nationwide lockdowns which have brought the people's life whether it is social or economic life to a standstill. The world has fallen silent and now all the resources have been diverted and shifted to meeting the never-experienced-before crisis. There is a multifaceted impact of the virus as the economic activities of nations are put on hold. The COVID-19 pandemic affected the manufacturing as well as the services sector such as tours and travels, retail, real estate, education, health, IT, banks, hotels, hospitality, healthcare, media, recreation, etc. The present study aims to assess the potential impact of second wave of COVID-19 on Indian economy. The study presents certain suggestions for the improvement of Indian economy and curtails the pandemic. With the long-drawn-out country-wide lockdown, worldwide economic downturn and associated distraction of demand and supply chains, the Indian economy is likely to face an extended period of slowdown. There is a debate going on in the country about ending of the lockdown and the Indian workforce returning to work. It is very difficult for the government to decide a choice between the health of the people and the health of the economy. And this is what is happening at present. The courts are asking the government to put lockdown to break the chain of COVID pandemic but the governments of various states believing that lockdown is the last option as poor people will suffer.

Keywords: Indian economy, economic recovery, COVID-19, lockdown, second wave.

INTRODUCTION

Even the Great Depression of 1930 was not as worse as COVID-19. Everyday analyst and rating agencies are reporting new bottoms of a fall down in economic activities. The COVID-19 has brought a social and economic life to a standstill. For an Indian economy, the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic is an exceptional shock. The economy was already in a paralyzed state before Covid-19 struck. With the long-drawn-out country-wide lockdown, worldwide economic downturn and associated distraction of demand and supply chains, the Indian economy is likely to face an extended period of slowdown. The scale of the economic impact will depend upon:

- the length and severity of the health crisis,
- the period of the lockdown and
- the manner in which the situation changes once the lockdown is lifted.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study aims at the following objectives:

- To assess the potential impact of second wave of COVID-19 on Indian economy;
- To present suggestions for the improvement of economy and curtail the pandemic.

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON VARIOUS SECTORS OF INDIAN ECONOMY

The outbreak of COVID-19 has impacted countries in a massive way, especially the nationwide lockdowns which have brought the people's life whether it is social or economic life to a standstill. The world has fallen silent and now all the resources have been diverted and shifted to meeting the never-

experienced-before crisis. There is a multifaceted impact of the virus as the economic activities of nations are put on hold.

The COVID-19 pandemic affected the manufacturing as well as the services sector such as tours and travels, retail, real estate, education, health, IT, banks, hotels, hospitality, healthcare, media, recreation, etc.

- 1) **Tourism Industry:** The industry is totally destroyed due to COVID 19. No tourist came to India since March 2020, as Government of India has stopped issue tourist visa since March 2020. As compared to year 2019, in the year 2020, 75 % less foreign tourist came to India because no tourist visa was issued since March 2020. As per Mr. Rajnish Kayasth, General Secretary of Indian Association of Tour Operators, the majority of members have suffered a setback of their business by 90 % and suffered a loss of Rs 60000 crores. Majority of operators either removed 80-90 % of their employees or sent on long leave without pay. It is one of the biggest hit industries in this world, this sector has suffered most from the recession without the direct involvement from the government. Since people are not likely to travel for leisure for months or years to come, it will impact the inflow of tourists in all the countries severely reducing the money flow in this sector.
- 2) **Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises:** MSME which have a credit of creating more than 90 % of the jobs in India, employing over 115 million people and contributing 30 % of the Gross Domestic Product, are under the pressure of severe cash crunch if the lockdown is extended to one or two months. Many of these MSMEs are carrying out their activities on financial assistance from banks and other financial institutions and they have loan obligations and monthly installments to pay. Many of them might not be able to operate if their cash cycle is disturbed due to lockdown, with fixed costs creating problem in such a situation. On the other hand, movement of perishable goods is hindered and thus, these businesses will suffer a huge loss. Indian economy is not in a position to have a real and sustainable growth without the contribution of MSME sector. The health crisis will also test the feasibility of Indian start-ups. Start-ups have to depend on cross-border fund raising. Several owners are seeing their businesses to a standstill. Receivables are enhancing and they have to undertake cost-reduction measures in their ventures. Indian Government will have to make funds available to MSME sector, as venture capital firms may not be interested nowadays or take a little longer time to come and support because of the global restrictions on capital inflows and outflows.
- 3) **Household Savings:** Due to COVID 19 and lockdown people are bound to stay at home during the last one year, so their expenses were curtailed down and thus increase in their household savings. As per brokerage firm Motilal Oswal, the household savings has reached up to 22.5 % of GDP. In 2019, the data was 19.8 %. However, during 2020 lockdown in April – June 2020 household savings reduced by 5.8 %. With the starting of unlock in Dec 2020, household savings was high at 13.7 %. This fluctuation was due to the reduction of income of people. According to RBI, in quarter ending June 2020 the non financial savings was stood at 21.4 % of GDP which was 10.4 % in September quarter and 8.4 % in December quarter. Before COVID the level was 7-8 % of GDP.
- 4) **Currency Circulation:** The currency circulation in Indian economy rose to all time high in two decades. As per RBI report, the currency circulation increases to Rs. 28.6 kharab by March 2021. It is 16.8 % higher than previous year. It is basically due to uncertainty caused by COVID 19. People started collecting more liquid cash for unforeseen circumstances. As per RBI Report, currency circulation as per the ratio of GDP was 14.6 % by March 2021, while in the year ended March 2020 this ratio was 12 %. Due to second wave of COVID 19, people are more reliant on liquid cash for the last 2 months. As per the data of RBI, cash with people was increased by Rs.

30191 crore to reach at new level of Rs. 2787941 crore as on April 09, 2021. From February 27 – April 09, 2021 the cash was Rs. 52928 crore.

- 5) **Demat Account:** In April 2020 to March 2021, there was a record increase in investors who joined stock exchange. As per the joint report of National Securities Depositories Limited (NSDL) and Central Depository Securities Limited (CDSL), new Demat A/c opened between April 2020 and March 2021 was 14.2 lakhs. It is 3 times more as compared to previous year of 4.9 lakhs demat a/c opened in Financial Year 2019-20, while the average demat a/c opened in last three years was 43 lakhs . 19 lakhs demat a/c opened only in the month of March 2021. In financial year 2021, investors got 68 % return in stock exchange. Share market gave more than 10 % return in 10 years long time. People stayed at home during lockdown, so they got time to study and analyse the behaviour of stock market and manage their portfolio. Women are now interested in opening demat a/c and investing in shares.
- 6) **GST Collection:** There is no effect of lockdown and pandemic on GST Collection. In the month of April 2021, there was a record collection of GST of Rs. 1.41 lakh crore.

Month	GST Collection (In Rs. Lakh Crore)
October 2020	1.05
November 2020	1.04
December 2020	1.15
January 2021	1.19
February 2021	1.13
March 2021	1.23
April 2021	1.41

- 7) **Export and Import:** The exports in the month of April 2021 increase 3 fold to \$ 30.21 arab. Maximum contribution in export was given by Engineering, Gems and Jewellery and Petroleum Products. However, imports also rose by 3 fold and due to which trade deficit rose by 2 times to \$15.24 arab. In April 2021, the maximum import was done of raw oil of \$10.8 arab. Next comes to import of gold of \$6.12 arab.

	April 2020	April 2021
Exports (In \$ Arab)	10.17	30.21
Imports (In \$ Arab)	17.09	45.45
Trade Deficit (In \$ Arab)	6.92	15.24

- 8) **Loss of Employment:** The second wave of COVID 19 results in a loss of 75 lakhs jobs in the month of April 2021. During this period, unemployment rate rose to 7.97 %. As per Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE), the rate of unemployment reaches at its peak in April 2021 which is highest during the last 4 months which was 9.1 % in December 2020. In March 2021, the unemployment rate was 6.5 %. Due to rapid increase in positive cases, the state governments are imposing lockdown and other restrictions, which results in slower down of business activities and people have to lose their jobs. Seeing the present situation, it is hoped that unemployment rate will rise in the month of May 2021.
- 9) **CARE Ratings:** For the financial year 2021-22, the rating agency has reduced the estimate of India’s economic development to 10.2 %. Previously, the estimate was 10.7 % to 10.9 %. In the last one month CARE ratings has amended the estimates for 3 years. CARE ratings in its report stated that the situations have changed drastically for the last 30 days. Rating agency has estimated the Gross Value Added at Rs. 136.82 lakh crore from 124.11 lakh crore from previous year. Agency estimated that lockdown in various states lead to decrease of GDP by 0.8 % to 1 %.
- 10) **Agricultural Exports:** During the financial year from April 2020 to February 2021 the export of agricultural produce was Rs. 2.74 lakh crore as compared to financial year 2019-20 when exports

was Rs. 2.31 lakh crore which is 16.88 % more. During the financial year from April 2020 to February 2021 the import of agricultural produce was Rs. 141034 crore as compared to financial year 2019-20 when imports was Rs. 137014 crore. Even in COVID conditions, the trade balance was in favour of India. The surplus stood at 132579.69 crore from 93907.76 crore.

- 11) **Education and E-learning:** The destructive effect of the pandemic has left educators and educational institutions with an instant need to step up and transform the way education is delivered to the students whether they are involved in higher education or intermediate level or at lower level. The crucial nature of quality of education is something no one can compromise on and especially higher educational institutions in our country have flawlessly transitioned into e-learning and online teaching with the common goal of students' progress and endless learning. Even many universities are taking online final examinations. But the important point here is that majority of the students belongs to rural areas. They do not have the means to study online. Majority of rural students do not have smart phones or laptops to study. Many areas in India do not have the facility of uninterrupted internet. So, government should provide phone and means of internet to the students instead of providing scholarship to them. However, it would not be overstated if one is to say that we step on e-learning within a very short span of time. The efforts of the teachers who adapted to innovative technology, video lessons and online live classes cannot be underestimated. With limited resources but high passion, Indian teachers across the country have been striving hard and will continue to deliver quality education to the students.
- 12) **Restaurant services:** The National Restaurant Association of India which represent the majority of restaurants in India had advised its members to close their dine-in services when the lockdown began which severely impacted the pubs, cafes, dine-ins and also food delivery platforms i.e. Swiggy and Zomato which faced drop of more than 60% in revenue.
- 13) **Automobile Sector:** As far as automobile sector is concerned there are lot of things which are be worried off:
 - Many companies are working with only 50% employees;
 - Chances of 30-35% decrease in sales in the month of April 2021;
 - Decrease in walk in customers by 40% in showroom;
 - Due to lockdown and increase of second wave of COVID cases, there is a decline of 40% booking of cars;
 - Hero Motocorp closes all its plants from April 22, 2021 till May 01, 2021;
 - There is an obstacle in supply chain of spare parts required by car manufacturing companies.

As per Society of Manufacturers of Electric Vehicles (SMEV), the sales of electric vehicles dropped t 236802 units down by 20%. Last year the sale was 295683 units (FY 2019-20). As per SMEV in financial year 2020-21, the sale of 3 wheelers electric vehicles reduced to 143837 units down by 6%. However, sale of 4 wheelers electric vehicles increase by 53%.

RELIEF FROM RESERVE BANK OF INDIA

The Reserve Bank of India on Wednesday May 05, 2021 announced a Covid package of Rs 50,000 crore for medical equipment suppliers, vaccine makers, hospitals, and even patients in need of funds to treat the disease, while opening up next round of reorganization of loans for individual and small borrowers for up to 2 years. The Rs 50,000 crore emergency health services loans, which can be given by commercial banks till March 31, 2022, will be classified as priority sector loans for three years or repayment, whichever is earlier. In case of priority sector loans, these are exempted from maintaining cash reserve ratio or statutory liquidity ratio, and so commercial banks can extend them at concessional rates also. RBI also announced targeted long-term repo operation for small finance banks of up to Rs 10,000 crore. This will be used for lending of up to Rs 10 lakh per borrower. RBI Governor also

announced that the second purchase of G-SEC for Rs 35,000 crore under G-SAP 1.0 will be conducted on May 20, 2021.

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

It is suggested that the Indian government should adopt a manifold approach to handle or deal with the economic crisis. It will have to gear up its machinery (RBI, Ministry of Finance, etc) to ensure a quick and strong recovery in the economy.

- 1) Major contributions are needed from the Reserve Bank of India, the commercial banks, the financial institutions and other agencies in planning and managing policies as per the demand of the circumstances.
- 2) It will have to motivate and involve the general public and private organizations in responding to the situation. The massive nature of the problem requires strong support from all the stakeholders. The Indian government should make it very clear to its citizens that each and everything should not be left to the government alone. A government has its own limitations. There is a limit up to which the Indian government alone can take on the crisis. A strong sense of responsibility will have to be inculcated amongst the general public, private organizations, entrepreneurs, employees and workers and all other non-government organizations.
- 3) The government should take steps to tackle the situation of black-marketing, hoarding of important medicines required for covid patients. The government should look into the supply chain of oxygen and other medicinal equipments to hospitals.
- 4) The economic stress has started and will grow rapidly with this second wave of COVID-19. On one hand lockdown results in the loss of productivity, on the other hand, it results in a sharp decline in demand for goods and services by the consumers, thus resulting in a fall down and collapse in economic activity. However, lockdown and social distancing are the only cost-effective tools available to prevent the spread of COVID-19.
- 5) COVID pandemic demands coordinated fiscal policy as well as monetary policy measures to deal with it. The fiscal measures include paying the bills related to healthcare raised by the pandemic. Providing for medicines, testing kits, ventilators, ICU beds, masks, gloves, quarantine wards, personal protection equipment and other equipment would mean a vast increase in healthcare spending. Public spending on healthcare in India is around 1.1 % of GDP. The government should increase it in the current fiscal year. The crisis emerging from the COVID-19 spread will pull down investment and consumption demand. The Central Government will have to enhance the spending in order to increase demand of the products. Support to different sectors of the economy will have to be given as a measure to enhance the investment demand. Monetary policy is not very effective in dealing with the present pandemic because the problem is not of liquidity alone. The distraction of economic activity and the future uncertainty generally brings down the investment sentiments in the country.

CONCLUSION

Global Brokerage Firm Barclays states that to save the economy from derailing, there is a need to control the pandemic. If the conditions remains worst and lockdown remains in force till June 2021, then Indian economy will lose \$38.4 arab (Rs. 2.83 lakh crore).

If the present conditions remains the same and restrictions of free movements prevails till August 2021, than the rate of growth may comes down to 8.8%. Barclays has cut the economic growth rate from 11% to 10%. It states that rise in positive cases and increase in death rate leads to uncertain environment which compels it to reduce the growth rate.

With International Labour Organization projecting that economy of many nations will recover in the second half of 2021, depending on COVID-19 vaccination rollout, India may expect its ruined economy to heal after kicking off its nationwide Covid-19 vaccination program. Many health economists assume that vaccination program in India may help in the recovery of the economy as the situation of women and children expected to improve with health programmes resuming after vaccination of health workers and more people joining the workforce.

There is a debate going on in the country about ending of the lockdown and the Indian workforce returning to work. It is very difficult for the government to decide a choice between the health of the people and the health of the economy. And this is what is happening at present. The courts are asking the government to put lockdown to break the chain of COVID pandemic but the governments of various states believing that lockdown is the last option as poor people will suffer. Economists believe that if the poor people do not die of pandemic, they will die of hunger if lockdown persists. Here it is important to note that Indian economy has a unique structure. 50 % of the Indian households still depend upon agriculture directly or indirectly. The people working in the subsistence sector cannot claim unemployment benefits because they are not a part of social security net. During hard times like now, they expect the state government to take care of their basic requirements of food and shelter. They are always ready to bounce back if basic requirements are taken care of. Central as well as state governments will have to look into the relief measures efficiently, so that the poor and the vulnerable sections does not suffer. Many philanthropists have also come forward to provide social security measures so that workforce of the country should not suffer.

REFERENCES

- 1) Radhika Pandey, A. P. (2020). *Covid-19 and MSMEs: The 'identification' problem*. Ideas for India for More Evidence Based Policy. <https://www.ideasforindia.in/topics/macroeconomics/covid-19-and-the-msme-sector-the-identification-problem.html>
- 2) <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0972262921989126>
- 3) <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0972063420935541>
- 4) <https://indianexpress.com/article/explained/explained-how-has-covid-19-affected-the-global-economy-6410494/>

Newspapers

- The Economic Times
- Business Standard
- Hindustan
- Amar Ujala